

MaxEnt, In(Probability) and the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law Distributions

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The idea of extremizing entropy (written as a function of $P(e/T)$ =probability, where e is single particle energy and T temperature, with respect to $P(e/T)$ including the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$ =constant leads to a recipe for entropy. This recipe involves solving $P(e/T)$ for e/T and then integrating with respect to $dP(e/T)$ so that d/dP from the extremization cancels the integration procedure. This recipe for entropy is thus based on: $dS/dP = e/T$ or more generally on $dS/dP = a + be/T$ where a and b are constant and the extra constraint $\sum_i P(e_i) = 1$ is used.

In general, $S(P)$, but we argue that in both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law Cases, dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$, which in information theory is called information. We consider how this is linked to taking the derivative d/d ($1/T$) of $dS/dP = e/T$ or its generalization.

MaxEnt and a Recipe for Entropy

The idea of extremizing entropy subject to constraints is considered a fundamental idea in statistical mechanics it seems, but it leads to a recipe because the constraint is usually $\sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$ =constant. Thus one seeks a function of $P(e_i/T)$, $F(P)$, such that $dF/dP = e_i/T$. This function may then be integrated with respect to dP to create the "entropy" function, with the derivative d/dP and integration over dP being inverse operations. As a result, one has:

$$dS/dP = e_i/T \quad ((1a))$$

One may add the extra constraint $\sum_i P(e_i/T) = 1$. In such a case, one might also write:

$$dS/dP = a + be_i/T \quad ((1b)) \text{ where } a \text{ and } b \text{ are constants.}$$

Thus one may add a term $A \sum_i P(e_i)$ to entropy and even a constant.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

In this case, $P(e_i/T) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ and entropy is taken as Shannon's entropy i.e.

$$S = - \sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(P) \quad ((2))$$

S is a function of P and $\ln(P)$, which is called information in information theory, but dS/dP is only a function of $\ln(P)$ i.e. of information.

Power Law Case

In (1), it is shown that a power law distribution:

$$P(e_i/T) = C (1 - k/T e_i)^{1/k} \quad ((3))$$

is a solution of the Zwanzig differential equation:

$$dP/dt \text{ partial} = 0 = -p/m dP/dx \text{ partial} + d/dp \text{ partial} [dV/dx + g(x,p)] P + d/dp \{ \text{partial} D(x,p) d/dp \text{ partial} P \} \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{with } e = pp/2m + V(x) \text{ and } D(x,p) = gmT (1 - ke/T) \quad ((5))$$

One may immediately see that $D(x,p)$ in ((5)) is of the form of dS/dp from MaxEnt theory.

{Aside: One may note that in other problems, a power law of the form: $P(e/T) = C (e_i/T)^{1/k}$ may appear.}

Using the entropy recipe discussed above, one should solve ((3)) for $1 - ke/T$ i.e.

$$\text{Exp} \{ k \ln(P/C) \} = dS/dP = 1 - ke/T \quad ((6))$$

One may see that like in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$, the information. Thus these seemingly very different distributions have a common feature.

Consequences of MaxEnt and dS/dP Being a Strict Function of $\ln(P)$

The maximum entropy (MaxEnt) recipe with a constraint on energy $\text{Sum over } i e_i P(e_i/T)$ and a possible linear term $\text{Sum over } i P(e_i) = 1$ allows one to write for the power law:

$$\text{Exp} \{ k \ln(P/C) \} = dS/dP = 1 - ke/T \quad ((6))$$

The question arises: What is the effect of information $\ln(P)$ on the form of the probability distribution P ? Given that $\ln(P)$ appears in dS/dP , if one wishes to take the derivative of ((6)) with respect to $1/T$, then $\ln(P/C)$ will give rise to a logarithmic derivative i.e.

$$dP/d(1/T) / P \quad ((7))$$

as well as $d/d\ln(P) (dS/dP)$.

Thus $d/d \ln(P)$ acting on dS/dP must essentially cancel the effect of $d/d(1/T)$ acting on P so that one has P in the numerator and denominator. The exponential form, with a linear $\ln(P)$ in the exponent of dS/dP means it returns itself (up to a multiplicative constant), but it is equal to $1 - keT$. Thus $d/d(1/T)$ should lower a power of $(1 - keT)$ in P so the two compensate to create P again which cancels with P in the denominator. Thus one has a power law distribution in $1 - ke/T$.

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case:

$$dS/dP = e/T = \ln(P/C) \quad ((8)) \quad (C=\text{normalization of } P)$$

$$d/d(1/T) \ln(P/C) = dP/d(1/T) / P \quad ((9))$$

$dP/d(1/T)$ returns itself and the multiplicative value e . This implies $P=C\exp(-e_i/T)$.

Conclusion

We note that both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law Distributions, which are seeming quite different, have a MaxEnt entropy S such that dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$ which is called information in information theory. If average energy $\sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$ and possibly $\sum_i P(e_i/T) = 1$ are the constraints, MaxEnt leads to:

$$dS/dP = a + b e_i/T \quad ((A)) \quad \text{where } a, b \text{ are constants}$$

in both the power law and MB cases. Given that dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$, taking $d/d(1/T)$ of the MaxEnt result ((A)) means: $d/d(1/T) \ln(P) = dP/d(1/T) / P$. Thus $d/d(\ln P)$ acting on dS/dP must have the inverse effect of $d/d(1/T)$. In both cases, this involves exponentials, but in different ways. One way to have $d/d(1/T)$ cancel $d/d(\ln P)$ acting on dS/dP is for dS/dP to be $\exp(k \ln(P))$. Then $d/d \ln(P)$ brings back dS/dP which is $1 - ke/T$ (multiplied by k). This compensates $d/d(1/T)$ if P is a power law in $(1 - ke/T)$. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, a similar argument applies, but in this case $dP/d(1/T)$ returns P multiplied by e which cancels P in the denominator.

Thus, $\ln(P)$ i.e. information, seems to be a feature connecting both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law distributions.